

Original Research

Identifying and Prioritizing Factors Behind Cyber loafing Use at Work Using Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MADM) Approach

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Abstract

The aim of the current paper is to identify the effective factors in forming the cyberloafing phenomenon and rank these factors. In the present study, a multiple attribute decision-making method has been used. The statistical population of this study consists of managers and employees of the Yazd Provincial Tax Administration, and 27 of them were selected based on accessibility. This research is applied and descriptive-analytical in terms of purpose and type. Based on the literature review, eighteen effective factors in the formation of cyberloafing were identified. Different MADM techniques, such as SAW, TOPSIS, ELECTRE, and TOXONOMY, were used to rank each factor. Finally, the Copeland fusion technique was used to reach a consensus on the execution of the mentioned techniques. Our investigations have shown that organizational policy factors, organizational commitment, and having a lot of leisure time had the most significant impact on the formation of the cyberloafing phenomenon. Also, interpersonal conflict, role overload, and belief in disorder had the least impact on the formation of the cyberloafing phenomenon. The current research is the first one conducted with this approach, especially in Iran, and its results can be considered by managers in other organizations as well.

Keywords: Copeland fusion technique, Cyberloafing, Information technology, Multiple attribute decision-making techniques (MADM).

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Introduction

The current period is often referred to as the age of information or knowledge, and information technology has developed as a new procedure and way of thinking that has affected each aspect of human life and work. The workplace has been essentially formed by this influence. In today's context, the notion of an organization appears to be inseparable from the presence and utilization of information technology (Kamar et al., 2023). The advantages of utilizing computer systems and social networks have become a common concern for all accomplished managers across many advanced nations. This concern has also cleared a new way for developing and less developed nations. Whenever a manager tries to improve an organization, one of the first necessities they recognize is the integration of information technology (automating administrative, financial, and organizational systems under their oversight). Despite the internet's considerable contributions to organizations in recent times, supporting the progression of their offerings, it has also brought a bunch of workplace deviant behaviors; one of these behaviors is cyberloafing (Prasetya et al., 2023). Cyberloafing is viewed as an undocumented behavior inside the work environment (Tsai, 2023; ZoghbiManrique de Lara & OlivaresMesa, 2010). It leads to unproductive use of work hours and encourages employees to avoid their commitments and tasks (El Din & Baddar, 2019; Usman et al., 2021).

Cyberloafing can be categorized into two dimensions: partial and severe. Partial loafing encompasses activities such as sending and receiving personal emails during work hours, browsing news and financial websites, and online shopping. On the other hand, severe loafing includes behaviors like accessing explicit websites, engaging in specific website visits, online chatting, maintaining blogs, participating in online gambling, and downloading movies and music (Blanchard & Henle, 2008; Rahman et al., 2022).

Certain researchers view cyberloafing as detrimental to employees, whereas others hold the belief that it might actually enhance employees' productivity (Blau et al., 2006; Peng et al., 2023). For instance, cyberloafing, like sending and receiving personal emails or making personal phone calls at work, can make employees feel more stimulated and excited (Rahaei & Salehzadeh, 2020). Furthermore, most internet users believe that quickly checking football scores online, using social networks, or sending a brief message to a friend takes only a few seconds and does not force any critical issues on the organization. However, these mere seconds can quickly accumulate into hours, posing challenges for company operations. Consequently, many managers share the perspective that cyberloafing contributes to the depletion of employees' energy (Lim & Teo, 2005; She & Li, 2023). Engaging in cyberloafing can give rise to several concerns, including jeopardizing the integrity of the information security system, consuming valuable bandwidth resources, putting customers' confidential information at risk, and causing delays in employees' tasks (Rahman et al., 2022; Zoghbi Manrique de Lara & Olivares Mesa, 2010).

Previous research has given minimal attention to the consequences of cyberloafing. Sawitri and Mayasari (2017) decided that distinctive cyberloafing activities have a

differential impact on employee creativity, wherein e-mailing and leisure activities increase creativity.

A few researchers discussed the negative impact of cyberloafing on employee behavior, performance, and organizational productivity (Alharthi et al., 2021; Askew and Buckner, 2017; Yildiz Durak and Saritepeci, 2019). Kaptangil et al. (2021) determined a partial and relatively low impact of cyberloafing on employees' organizational identification and motivation within the tourism division. In the meantime, Andel et al. (2019) found cyberloafing to moderate the association between introduction to verbal and physical aggression with job satisfaction and turnover intention within the workplace. Three dimensions of cyberloafing (recovery, deviant, and development behaviors) were also found to be significantly related to job performance by Baskaran et al. (2019). Hadlington and Parsons (2017) determined Internet addiction and cyberloafing to be critical predictors of employees' information security awareness, though Yildiz Durak and Saritepeci (2019) found cyberloafing to predict job burnout. Farivar and Richardson (2020), who conceptualized cyberloafing to reflect spillover social media, determined that it positively affected the work satisfaction of single and childless employees and non-work satisfaction among childless but married men. Wu et al. (2020) determined that employees' engagement with online social activities, or social cyberloafing, is positively related to psychological detachment, leading to weakness.

The authors also found psychological detachment to mediate positively and weariness to negatively mediate the association of cyberloafing with employees' mental health, subsequently calling attention to the truth that cyberloafing may have positive results for employee well-being in a few situations. Syrek et al. (2018) found that social media use for non-work or personal reasons during working hours was related to lower work engagement. However, work engagement increased an hour after such cyberloafing activity, which gives little assurance to the supposition that cyberloafing may act as a micro-break for employees in a few instances.

Despite various research projects addressing cyberloafing, its presence in the workplace remains a complex and unresolved matter. While international research has shed light on the challenges posed by cyberloafing, there has been limited exploration of this issue in Iran. Thus, due to the newness of this subject within the administration domain of the nation, conducting research on this topic within the government sector becomes imperative. Previous studies have essentially inspected the links between managerial variables and cyberloafing, identifying potential positive outcomes. However, the factors contributing to the emergence of cyberloafing have only been briefly touched upon. Notably, prior research has not utilized Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MADM) techniques to rank these factors. Therefore, incorporating such methodologies in domestic research concerning this subject becomes essential. The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Finance, a pivotal sector within the country, holds diverse objectives, including the regulation of economic and financial policies, preparation and oversight of the nation's annual budget performance, coordination of economic and technical collaborations between Iran and other nations, and management of international economic and financial interactions. Given this, identifying factors influencing the efficacy and productivity of its employees is crucial. Cyberloafing stands out as a significant factor impacting this domain. Given employees' escalating usage of digital tools and the internet for daily tasks

and services, the absence of research on internet misuse within this ministry highlights the necessity to identify the factors influencing the cyberloafing phenomenon. This study focuses on the Tax Affairs Organization of Yazd province, an affiliated institution of this ministry, aiming to categorize and rank these factors to unveil the most influential ones and implement appropriate strategies for mitigation. Considering these circumstances, the present study addresses the question of which factors contribute to the emergence of cyberloafing among employees in the Tax Affairs Organization of Yazd province and which of these factors hold the greatest significance.

Theoretical foundations

Information Technology and Cyberloafing

Suppose cyberloafing pertains to employees utilizing company-provided Internet resources for work-related activities, such as checking personal emails or browsing websites unrelated to their tasks. In that case, it can also be regarded as a challenge within the realm of information technology (Tsai, 2023). Indeed, these activities can potentially detrimentally affect employees' work routines. For instance, extended periods devoted to non-work-related tasks can reduce employee efficiency. Moreover, it can lead to amplified demands on bandwidth and internet speed, incurring additional costs.

Additionally, there is a heightened likelihood of security risks within the organization. For instance, accessing unsafe websites with high-security risks might pave the way for external individuals to breach the organization's systems and pilfer sensitive information (Askew, 2012). Hence, it can be affirmed that cyberloafing holds a significant position within the scope of information technology. This necessitates the formulation and execution of pertinent remedies to effectively oversee and regulate the utilization of information technology resources within organizations. For instance, devising internet usage policies, overseeing employee actions, providing education and training about security vulnerabilities, and enhancing the management of information technology resources can collectively contribute to upholding security measures and enhancing organizational efficiency (Prasetya et al., 2023).

Numerous scholarly investigations within the realm of information technology have highlighted cyberloafing as a noteworthy concern and a security challenge. These studies have characterized cyberloafing as the utilization of information technology resources provided by the company for tasks unrelated to work, like perusing personal emails or navigating websites that have no connection to the job (Prasetya et al., 2023; Rahman et al., 2022). An investigation into the correlation between cyberloafing and employee performance has revealed that engaging in cyberloafing can adversely affect employee performance. Cyberloafing may result in reduced concentration and attention from employees, diminished productivity, and an elevated level of security risks within the organization. In another study, the repercussions of cyberloafing on the organization's cyber security were explored. The findings underscored that utilizing information technology resources for non-work-related pursuits can compromise organizational cyber security, heightening security risks and opening pathways for external intrusion into the organization's systems. Consequently, scientific research underscores cyberloafing is a noteworthy and grave concern in information technology. It calls for strategic planning

and implementing fitting remedies to effectively oversee and regulate the utilization of information technology resources within organizations.

Cyberloafing

The term "cyberloafing" or "internet loafing" is constructed from two components: "cyber," relating to the domain of computers and information, and "loafing," which characterizes someone not utilizing their available time judiciously and squandering it. Consequently, cyberloafing encompasses a range of electronic behaviors and activities in the workplace wherein an employee engages in actions that the supervisor does not consider part of their job responsibilities. In the present era marked by substantial technological advancements, we are witnessing inappropriate internet usage, both within and outside of work settings. These behaviors and inclinations can be attributed to societal structures, a lack of technological literacy, and the online environments that facilitate such deviations and disregard for proper usage. Cyberloafing is characterized as the deliberate utilization of information technology for activities unrelated to work, carried out within working hours, and not demanding substantial technological expertise (Jandaghi et al., 2015). Numerous studies indicate that a range of factors—both individual, such as personality traits, demographics, job attitudes, and self-control, and situational, including job characteristics, job stressors, and organizational policies—play a role in influencing cyberloafing. Other research endeavors focus on revealing the underlying mechanisms of cyberloafing, proposing that employees resort to cyberloafing as a means to disconnect from their tasks or to alleviate stress arising from their jobs, thereby utilizing their spare time at the workplace (Peng et al., 2023).

In certain instances, cyberloafing may be viewed as detrimental to both employees and organizations. However, conversely, cyberloafing could yield advantages by affording employees the opportunity to learn more effectively via constructive leisure activities. Temporary staff within organizations might acquire the requisite skills and professional knowledge for task execution through cyberloafing. Consequently, they can evolve into more valuable and beneficial organizational contributors. In essence, cyberloafing resembles taking a physical break that allows individuals to disengage from ongoing activities momentarily. This ultimately prompts the activation of the subconscious mind, aiding in the assimilation and analysis of substantial information (Wong et al., 2023). The excessive utilization of the internet, particularly for non-academic pursuits, stands as a growing personal and societal challenge. This trend places supplementary burdens on organizations due to Internet resources' improper and unproductive employment. Researchers have classified cyberloafing as a behavior with repercussions, including diminished employee effectiveness, decreased productivity, concerns regarding human mistreatment and misconduct, and a general misapplication of the internet. Furthermore, they contend that excessive internet usage can spawn undesirable consequences such as the compromise of intellectual property, entanglement in legal disputes, instances of sexual harassment, dwindled productivity due to extensive web browsing, security vulnerabilities, and heightened network bandwidth consumption (Tehrani et al., 2023).

As the current study seeks to pinpoint the factors influencing the emergence of cyberloafing, our next step involves delving into the research that has addressed these factors.

The conclusions drawn from De Lara's study in 2007, focusing on the influence of organizational justice on cyberloafing behavior, revealed that when employees perceive a lack of fairness within the organization, it prompts them to partake in cyberloafing activities. Additionally, the inclination to engage in inappropriate behaviors like cyberloafing is heightened among employees who hold a belief in disorderliness (De Lara, 2007).

In a different study, Eddy et al. (2010) explored employees' personal activities during their working hours. The findings indicated that employees allocate around 5 hours to personal activities within the workweek. Of this time, over 90% is dedicated to personal internet use, checking personal emails, making phone calls, or conversing with colleagues. Employees indulge in cyberloafing behavior for various reasons, including fatigue, boredom, convenient internet access, and ample free time (Eddy et al., 2010).

In a separate study conducted by Runing Sawitri (2012), the investigation centered on the influence of job stress on cyberloafing behavior. The outcomes of this study revealed a substantial correlation between these two variables, indicating an added dimension to the connection between stress and cyberloafing behavior (RuningSawitri, 2012).

Jia et al. (2013) explored the impact of personality traits on cyberloafing. Their findings indicated that self-control, gender, conscientiousness, emotional stability, and internet usage policies negatively correlate with cyberloafing. On the other hand, extroversion demonstrated a positive and notable connection with cyberloafing (Jia et al., 2013).

In their study, Moody and Siponen (2013) named their research on personal Internet use and cyberloafing "Employees' Reactions to Role Ambiguity and Role Conflict: A Study of Personal Internet Use." Their findings indicated that employees commonly resort to personal internet use as a reaction to role ambiguity and conflict. Moreover, when employees perceive a lesser likelihood of facing penalties for personal internet use, they tend to engage in such behavior more frequently, using it to manage the challenges of role ambiguity and role conflict (Moody & Siponen, 2013).

Ahmed et al. (2014) explored the negative impact of role conflict on employee performance. Role conflict emerges when significant disparities exist between expectations and assessments. Many present-day institutions grapple with conflicts within their organizations. Not only do they expend time addressing these conflicts, but they also invest considerable effort in resolving this significant issue (Ahmed et al., 2014).

Oosthuizen et al. (2018) explored the correlation between cyberloafing and organizational justice, work engagement, and employee trust. Their findings revealed that when employees perceive their organization as just and equitable, it fosters growth in trust. This heightened trust, in turn, contributes to an increase in work engagement, ultimately resulting in a reduction in cyberloafing behavior (Oosthuizen et al., 2018).

Rahayuningsih and Putra (2018) examined how information deficiency and organizational commitment influence the internet loafing behavior of lecturers within the ASEAN Economic Community. Their study revealed a connection between competitive

intelligence, work commitment, and cyberloafing behavior (Rahayuningsih & Putra, 2018).

In a separate study, Razmi et al. (2018) demonstrated that variables unrelated to the internet, self-efficacy, favorable attitudes towards cyberloafing, and perceived cyberloafing among co-workers serve as significant predictors of online cyberloafing (Razmi et al., 2018).

Sao et al. (2020) conducted an investigation to gather insights into cyberloafing and its influence on employee conduct. The central aim of this research was to probe into the origins of cyberloafing among employees and the diverse cyberloafing activities transpiring in the professional setting. The study extensively examined the substantial impact of cyberloafing on both employee performance and behavior. The research encompassed a participant pool of 172 employees hailing from various departments. The outcomes underscored that cyberloafing activities wield a noteworthy and positive influence on behavioral aspects encompassing recuperation from work, acquiring new skills, engagement with developmental websites, taking breaks, personal advancement, and skill development. Furthermore, these activities displayed a significant positive sway on influential facets like generating novel ideas, augmenting workplace appeal, rekindling attention, fostering excitement and enthusiasm, and enhancing work performance (Sao et al., 2020).

In an alternate investigation, Rahman et al. (2022) explored the favorable impacts of cyberloafing and the alignment between individuals and the organization on employee performance. Moreover, this study investigates whether innovative work behavior assumes a mediating role within this connection. The study employed quantitative structural equation modeling using the method of partial least squares, along with data garnered from online questionnaires administered to 210 employees within the banking industry of Indonesia. These employees held internet access privileges during work hours and were authorized to engage in non-work activities, including cyberloafing. The findings of this study reveal a positive correlation between innovative work behavior and cyberloafing and person-organization fit. Furthermore, the study highlights that innovative work behavior functions as an intermediary variable in the relationship between cyberloafing, person-organization fit, and employee performance (Rahman et al., 2022)

Aryani Ghizghapan et al. (2022) conducted a study to construct a model that illustrates the interplay of organizational factors, job conflict, and toxic leadership in the context of online cyberloafing. This research employed a quantitative approach and utilized a descriptive-correlational technique. The study's target population encompassed personnel from comprehensive universities associated with the Ministry of Science, Research, and Technology across four tiers: international, national, regional, and local performance throughout the nation. The outcomes of this investigation revealed that the influential organizational factors affecting cyberloafing could be represented by an input layer comprising seven nodes and a hidden layer with three nodes (Aryani ghizghapan et al., 2022).

Tehrani et al. (2023) conducted a study titled "Identification of Precursors and Outcomes of Cyberloafing using a Fuzzy Delphi Approach." The study aimed to identify the factors leading to cyberloafing and its subsequent effects within the Tehran University of Jihad organization context. The study incorporated a qualitative segment utilizing the fuzzy Delphi approach. In this regard, research papers concerning the factors preceding cyberloafing and its consequences, published between 2002 and 2021, were gathered and evaluated from reputable databases. A total of 68 sources were utilized for the ultimate analysis. The quantitative segment involved a purposive selection of 20 experts and specialists affiliated with the Tehran University of Jihad organization. The fuzzy Delphi approach was employed to validate the conclusions of the qualitative component. The study's findings delineated the antecedents of cyberloafing across three primary categories: structural, behavioral, and environmental factors. Additionally, the consequences of cyberloafing were categorized into two groups: positive and negative outcomes. The outcomes of this research offer the potential to enhance the management of employee cyberloafing within the organizational setting, thereby mitigating its unfavorable and detrimental repercussions (Tehrani et al., 2023).

In a study grounded in the conservation of resources theory, Tsai (2023) examined the daily dynamics encompassing cyberloafing, creativity, and proactive behavior. Furthermore, the study delved into the favorable influence of the work environment. The study involved the participation of 94 full-time employees from China who completed a questionnaire for a continuous span of 10 working days. The outcomes demonstrated that cyberloafing positively predicts employee creativity and proactive behavior. Moreover, it fosters informal interactions and contributes to the quality of the work environment, thereby enhancing the constructive associations between cyberloafing and employee creativity and proactive behavior. The conclusions derived from this research possess noteworthy theoretical and practical implications (Tsai, 2023).

Method

Participants

The statistical population for this study comprised 27 employees of the Tax Affairs Organization in Yazd Province. From this population, 27 experts were selected using a targeted sampling method of the snowball type. To identify the factors influencing cyberloafing, we identified eighteen factors after an extensive review of the research literature. These factors were then examined through a questionnaire. Since the criteria used in the questionnaire were based on theoretical foundations and previous studies and had been approved by professors and experts for both the quantity and quality of the questions, content validity was confirmed.

Furthermore, the questionnaire also demonstrated face validity, as experts and specialists confirmed the tool's clarity and lack of ambiguity in the questions. In this study, we employed Cronbach's alpha to determine the questionnaire's reliability. The results indicated a reliability of 78% (values above 0.70 are considered acceptable). Additionally, multi-criteria decision-making techniques were utilized to prioritize these factors, which will be briefly described below.

Measurements

Multiple Attribute Decision Making (MADM)

Multiple Attribute Decision Making (MADM) is a decision-making model that has gained significant popularity over the last two decades and finds widespread applications in complex decision-making scenarios that involve multiple, and at times conflicting, criteria (Alamleh et al., 2023). The strength of these techniques lies in their ability to simplify the decision-making process by concurrently considering both qualitative and quantitative criteria. They provide a structured framework for addressing decision-making challenges, ultimately making them accessible to decision-makers across various domains (Liu et al., 2020). These techniques transform decision-making problems into a matrix format, as illustrated in the table below, and then conduct the necessary analyses.

Table 1. Decision Matrix

	X ₁	X ₂	...	X _n
A1	r ₁₁	r ₁₂	...	r _{1n}
A2	r ₂₁	r ₂₂	...	r _{2n}
...
A _m	r _{m1}	r _{m2}	...	r _{mn}

In this matrix, A_i represents option i, x_j represents attribute j, and r_{ij} represents the value of attribute j for option i (Azar et al., 2012). In a Multiple Attribute Decision Making (MADM) model, the best option would be a hypothetical option A^{*} that provides the highest preference (utility) from all available attributes; in other words, A^{*} is the option that maximizes the overall value of the decision matrix.

$$A^* \approx \{c_1^*, c_2^*, \dots, c_n^*\} \rightarrow c_j^* = \max_{i=1,2,\dots,m} U_j(c_{ij})$$

Due to the large number of Multiple Attribute Decision Making (MADM) techniques available, this study employs four commonly used techniques in the field of MADM, each of which analyses the problem based on a particular logic and theory. These techniques include TOPSIS, ELECTREE, SAW, and TOXONOMY, briefly explained below (Alamleh et al., 2023).

Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS)

The TOPSIS technique was proposed by Hwang and Yoon in 1981 and is one of the best Multiple Attribute Decision Making (MADM) techniques (Dutta et al., 2021). In this method, options are evaluated based on n attributes, and the concept is based on the idea that the selected option should have the shortest distance to the positive ideal solution (the best possible state, +A_i) and the longest distance to the negative ideal solution (the worst possible state, -A_i). The assumption is that the desirability of each attribute is uniformly increasing or decreasing. Solving the problem using the TOPSIS method involves 6 steps, as follows (Yoon & Hwang, 1995):

Step 1: Transforming the decision matrix into a dimensionless matrix as follows:

$$n_{ij} = \frac{r_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m r_{ij}^2}}, (j = 1, \dots, n)$$

The resulting matrix is called the Normalized Decision Matrix (ND).

Step 2: Forming the weighted normalized decision matrix:

$$V = N_D \cdot W_{mn}$$

Where V is the weighted normalized decision matrix and W is a diagonal matrix of the weights obtained for the attributes.

Step 3: Determining the positive and negative ideal solutions using the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} A^+ &= \{(\max v_{ij} I_j \in J), (\min v_{ij} I_j \in J')\} & A^- &= \{(\min v_{ij} I_j \in J), (\max v_{ij} I_j \in J')\} \\ A^+ &= \{V_1^+, V_2^+, \dots, V_N^+\} & A^- &= \{V_1^-, V_2^-, \dots, V_N^-\} \\ J &= \{j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\} \xrightarrow{j} \text{profit} & J' &= \{j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\} \xrightarrow{j} \text{cost} \end{aligned}$$

In these equations, the optimal values for positive attributes are the highest values, while for negative attributes, the optimal values are the lowest. Conversely, the least favorable values for positive attributes are the lowest, and for negative attributes, they are the highest.

Step 4: Calculating the distances of the options from the positive and negative ideal solutions using the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} d_i^- &= \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^-)^2 \right\}^{1/2} \\ d_i^+ &= \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^+)^2 \right\}^{1/2} \end{aligned}$$

Step 5: Calculating the relative closeness: In this step, the relative closeness of each option to the ideal solution is calculated by dividing the distance from the negative ideal solution by the sum of the distances from the positive and negative ideal solutions, as shown in the equation below:

$$C_i^+ = \frac{d_i^-}{d_i^+ + d_i^-}$$

Step 6: Ranking the options: Finally, the options are ranked based on their relative closeness values, with the option having the highest relative closeness value being the best option.

Elimination and Choice Translating Reality (ELECTRE)

The ELECTRE technique was introduced in the late 1980s and garnered recognition as one of the most effective Multiple Attribute Decision Making (MADM) methods (Tzeng & Huang, 2011). Its fundamental premise revolves around superior ranking relationships, which may not always result in the ranking of options but can help eliminate certain options from consideration. The steps for implementing this technique are outlined as follows (Tooranloo et al., 2020):

Step 1: Converting the decision matrix to a weighted normalized matrix.

$$n_{ij} = \frac{r_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m r_{ij}^2}}, (j = 1, \dots, n)$$

Step 2: Forming the weighted normalized matrix:

$$V = N_D \cdot W_{mn}$$

In which V is a weighted normalized matrix and W is a diagonal matrix of weights obtained for the attributes.

Step 3: Determining the concordance and discordance sets is a crucial step in the process. During this stage, a comprehensive evaluation of all options is conducted for each attribute, resulting in the formation of both concordance and discordance matrices. The concordance matrix quantifies the level of agreement among options for each attribute, while the discordance matrix quantifies the degree of disagreement among options for each attribute. These matrices play a vital role in calculating the relative proximity of each option to the ideal solution in the subsequent stages of the ELECTRE method.

Step 4: The next step involves the calculation of the concordance and discordance matrices. These matrices are computed using the weighted normalized matrix and the assigned weights for each attribute. The concordance matrix assesses the degree to which each option is preferred over other options concerning each attribute, whereas the discordance matrix evaluates the degree to which each option is less favorable than other options with regard to each attribute.

Step 5: In this step, we generate the effective concordance matrix by comparing the concordance values of each option to a predefined threshold value. Options that have concordance values exceeding the threshold are considered effectively concordant.

Step 6: In this step, we establish the effective discordance matrix by comparing the discordance values of each option to an average discordance value. Options with discordance values lower than the average are considered effectively discordant.

Step 7: Determining the overall effective matrix H is a crucial step. This matrix signifies the ranking order of different solutions relative to each other. In other words, if H_{ij} equals 1, it indicates that solution i is preferred over solution j.

Step 8: Eliminating non-effective options involves identifying the preferred option, typically the one with the fewest occurrences of "1" in the effective concordance matrix column. Non-effective options are then removed from the ranking.

The Simple Additive Weighting (SAW) model

The Simple Additive Weighting (SAW) model is one of the simplest techniques for multi-criteria decision making. By calculating the weights of the criteria (W_j), the most suitable option (A^*) can be determined. The steps to execute this technique are as follows (Vinogradova, 2019):

Step 1: Formation of the decision matrix: Based on the number of criteria and the number of options for each criterion, the decision matrix is formed as follows:

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ \vdots & \dots & \dots \\ x_{m1} & \dots & x_{mn} \end{bmatrix}$$

Step 2: Normalizing the decision matrix: In this step, the criteria with different dimensions are transformed into dimensionless criteria, and the matrix R is defined as follows:

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & \dots & r_{1n} \\ \vdots & \dots & \dots \\ r_{m1} & \dots & r_{mn} \end{bmatrix}$$

To normalize positive and negative criteria, the following equations are used:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\max_i \{x_{ij}\}}$$

$$r_{ij} = \frac{\frac{1}{x_{ij}}}{\max_i \left\{ \frac{1}{x_{ij}} \right\}} = \frac{\min_i \{x_{ij}\}}{x_{ij}}$$

Step 3: Determining the weight vector of the criteria: In this step, the weight vector of the criteria $[w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n]$ is defined based on the importance coefficient of each criterion in the decision-making process.

Step 4: Determining the best option: In this step, the best option is determined using the following formula:

$$A^* = \left\{ A_i \mid \max \frac{\sum_j w_j r_{ij}}{\sum_j w_j} \right\}$$

The options are ranked based on their weights, and the option with the highest weight is preferred.

Taxonomy analysis

Taxonomy analysis stands as a straightforward multi-criteria decision-making approach widely employed across various domains. Originally introduced by Adanson in 1763, its evolution continued with the contributions of a cohort of mathematicians in the 1950s. In this method, potential choices undergo evaluation and are subsequently arranged in a ranking sequence grounded in a predefined set of indicators. The execution of this technique involves the following steps:

Step 1: Formation of the decision matrix: In this step, the analyst or group of experts evaluate m options (A_1 to A_m) based on n indicators (C_1 to C_n).

Step 2: Formation of the standard (normalized) matrix Z : In this step, using the positive and negative ideal, positive and negative indicators are standardized, and the standard matrix Z is formed.

Step 3: Determination of the composite distance between options: In this step, using the standard matrix Z , the distance of each option from other options in relation to each indicator is calculated.

Step 4: Determination of the shortest distance: In this step, the minimum distance of each row in the matrix is determined as the shortest distance of each option. Then, the average and standard deviation of the shortest distances are determined.

Step 5: Homogenization of options: In this step, heterogeneous options are removed from the set.

Step 6: Determination of the pattern of options: In this step, the distance of each option from the ideal value in step 4 is obtained.

Step 7: Ranking of options: In this step, the level of development of each option is ranked.

Findings

Initially, by reviewing the research literature, eighteen factors were extracted as effective factors in the formation of cyberloafing, which can be observed in Table 2.

Table 2. Factors influencing cyberloafing

Row	Factor	Source
1	Organizational policy	(Blanchard & Henle, 2008; Jandaghi et al., 2015; Zoghbi Manrique-de-Lara & Olivares-Mesa, 2010)
2	Injustice in the organization	(Ahmadi et al., 2011; Freimark, 2012; Lim & Teo, 2005; Restubog et al., 2011; Tsai, 2023; Zoghbi Manrique-de-Lara & Olivares-Mesa, 2010)
3	Role conflict	(Blanchard & Henle, 2008; Freimark, 2012; Moody & Siponen, 2013; Prasetya et al., 2023)
4	Personality traits	(Jia et al., 2013; Restubog et al., 2011; She & Li, 2023)
5	Fatigue	(Eddy et al., 2010; Jandaghi et al., 2015; Prasetya et al., 2023)
6	Having a lot of free time	(Eddy et al., 2010; She & Li, 2023)
7	Boredom	(Cheng et al., 2020; Eddy et al., 2010; Prasetya et al., 2023)
8	Easy internet access	(Aftab, 2003; Eddy et al., 2010; Rahman et al., 2022)
9	Role ambiguity	(Blanchard & Henle, 2008; Moody & Siponen, 2013; Wong et al., 2023)
10	Interpersonal conflict	(Cheng et al., 2020; De Lara, 2007; Wong et al., 2023)
11	Job monotony	(Rahman et al., 2022; Sheikh et al., 2019)
12	Job stress	(Cheng et al., 2020; She & Li, 2023)
13	Role overload	(Jandaghi et al., 2015; Wong et al., 2023)
14	Belief in randomness	(Rahman et al., 2022; Sheikh et al., 2019)
15	Job dissatisfaction	(Cheng et al., 2020; Prasetya et al., 2023)
16	Employee attitude towards job	(Sheikh et al., 2019; Tsai, 2023)
17	Internet addiction	(Cheng et al., 2020; Wong et al., 2023)
18	Organizational commitment failure	(Cheng et al., 2020; Prasetya et al., 2023; Rahaei & Salehzadeh, 2020)

After identifying the factors, the research questionnaire was designed and provided to the experts, who were asked to rate these factors based on a Likert scale of five values. The frequency distribution and percentage of respondents based on demographic characteristics are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Absolute and relative frequency of employees based on demographic characteristics.

Demographic characteristics		Frequency	Relative frequency	Total
Gender	Male	18	66.66	27
	Female	9	33.34	
Educational attainment	Bachelor's degree	1	3.7	27
	Master's degree	22	81.5	
	Doctorate degree	4	14.80	
Employment history	Less than 10 years	12	44.45	27
	Between 10 and 20 years	14	51.85	
	More than 20 years	1	3.7	
Age	20 to 30 years old	1	3.7	27
	31 to 40 years old	21	77.78	
	41 to 50 years old	5	18.52	
	51 years old and above	0	0	

After collecting the data obtained from expert opinions, a decision matrix was formed. The results of applying the above-mentioned techniques can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Ranking of Factors Affecting the Formation of Internet Addiction Phenomenon Based on Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Techniques

Factor	SAW		TOPSIS		TOXONOMY		ELECTREE	
	w_i	Rank	c_i^+	Rank	c_i^-	Rank	Number of row preferences over column preferences	Rank
Perception of organizational policy	0.8558	1	0.753906	2	0.4981	1	14	1
Injustice or unfairness in the organization	0.7101	6	0.617956	6	0.6387	3	10	4
Role conflict	0.7254	5	0.680664	4	0.6463	4	11	2
Personality traits	0.7623	3	0.638733	5	0.5746	2	9	6
Fatigue	0.5838	11	0.582555	7	0.8829	17	4	9
Having a lot of free time	0.7314	4	0.701085	3	0.8441	13	11	2
Boredom	0.5486	14	0.516512	9	0.8764	16	3	11
Easy access to the internet	0.6821	8	0.561048	8	0.7694	11	6	7
Role ambiguity	0.5503	13	0.340647	16	0.7094	7	1	13
Interpersonal conflict	0.5406	16	0.333333	17	0.7308	10	1	13
Job uniformity	0.6407	9	0.463677	11	0.6724	6	5	8

Factor	SAW		TOPSIS		TOXONOMY		ELECTREE	
	w_i	Rank	c_i^+	Rank	c_i^-	Rank	Number of row preferences over column preferences	Rank
Job stress	0.5548	12	0.356631	15	0.7719	12	1	13
Task overload	0.5035	17	0.411255	13	1.0105	18	1	13
Belief in chaos	0.4537	18	0.25698	18	0.8716	15	0	18
Job dissatisfaction	0.5439	15	0.368911	14	0.8541	14	1	13
Employee perception of their job	0.6335	10	0.415836	12	0.7151	9	3	11
Internet addiction	0.6938	7	0.475417	10	0.7109	8	4	9
Lack of organizational commitment	0.8188	2	0.758921	1	0.6559	5	10	4

As shown in Table 4, the results of implementing the SAW technique indicate that the organizational policy factor with a relative weight of 85.0 has the highest importance. Therefore, among the factors affecting internet addiction, this factor has the greatest impact, and the factors of organizational commitment and personality traits, with relative weights of 81.0 and 76.0, are the second and third priorities, respectively. The results of employing the TOPSIS technique indicate that organizational commitment, perception of organizational policy, and having much free time, respectively, have the highest proximity coefficients and are recognized as the main influencing factors on the formation of internet addiction. The results of implementing the ELECTREE technique show that perception of organizational policy, role conflict, and having much free time have the greatest impact compared to other factors affecting internet addiction. Additionally, the results of implementing the TOXONOMY technique indicate that perception of organizational policy with a coefficient of 49.0, personality traits with a coefficient of 57.0, and organizational injustice with a coefficient of 63.0 have the highest priority compared to other factors. Considering the different results obtained from various MADM techniques, it can be seen that different prioritizations have been obtained for a single issue. Since each of these techniques has its strengths and weaknesses, an integrative approach using the Copeland method has been used in this study to achieve consensus in various prioritizations. The explanation of this technique will be provided later.

Copeland method

In this technique, pairwise comparison matrices are constructed for evaluating decision-making options. Suppose the count of preferences favoring one option over another surpasses the count of defeats of that same option against another. In that case, it is denoted as "M" within the pairwise comparison matrix. Conversely, if a clear majority or equal votes are lacking, it is marked with "X." In this context, "M" signifies that the corresponding row is favored over the respective column, while "X" indicates the column

is preferred over the row. The cumulative value of entries in each column indicates the number of defeats sustained by each option. In the application of this method, options are ranked based on the discrepancy between the quantity of preferences and the quantity of defeats. These principles are illustrated through Tables 5 and 6 in the methodology (Özdağoğlu et al., 2021).

Table 5. Pairwise comparison results and the number of wins and losses for each component.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	Σc	
1	-	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	17
2	X	-	X	X	M	X	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	X	12
3	X	M	-	X	M	X	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	X	13
4	X	M	X	-	M	X	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	X	13
5	X	X	X	X	-	X	M	X	M	M	X	M	M	M	M	X	X	X	X	7
6	X	M	M	X	M	-	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	X	14
7	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	M	X	X	M	M	M	X	X	X	X	4
8	X	X	X	X	M	X	M	-	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	X	X	10
9	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	M	X	X	M	M	M	X	X	X	X	4
10	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	M	M	X	X	X	X	X	2
11	X	X	X	X	M	X	M	X	M	M	-	M	M	M	M	M	X	X	X	9
12	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	M	M	X	-	M	M	M	X	X	X	X	5
13	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	M	X	X	X	X	X	1
14	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	0
15	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	M	X	X	M	M	-	X	X	X	X	3
16	X	X	X	X	X	X	M	X	M	M	X	M	M	M	M	-	X	X	X	7
17	X	X	X	X	M	X	M	X	M	M	X	M	M	M	M	M	-	X	X	9
18	X	M	X	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	-	15
ΣR	0	5	2	2	9	2	11	6	12	15	7	11	16	17	14	9	6	1		

Table 6. Final ranking of criteria based on the Copeland method

Component	ΣC	ΣR	$\Sigma C - \Sigma R$	Rank
Perception of organizational policy	17	0	17	1
Injustice or unfairness in the organization	12	5	7	5
Role conflict	13	2	11	4
Personality traits	13	2	11	4
Fatigue	7	9	-2	9
Having a lot of free time	14	2	12	3
Boredom	4	11	-7	11
Easy access to the internet	10	6	4	6
Role ambiguity	4	12	-8	12
Interpersonal conflict	2	15	-13	14

Component	$\sum C$	$\sum R$	$\sum C - \sum R$	Rank
Job uniformity	9	7	2	8
Job stress	5	11	-6	10
Task overload	1	16	-15	15
Belief in chaos	0	17	-17	16
Job dissatisfaction	3	14	-11	13
Employee perception of their job	7	9	-2	9
Internet addiction	9	6	3	7
Lack of organizational commitment	15	1	14	2

Discussion

Over the past two decades, remarkable strides in information technology have triggered substantial global changes. The evolution of information technology and the internet represents a pivotal transformation that ushers in the era of abundant information. The internet's expansion, akin to any revolutionary innovation, has engendered shifts across various domains of life. Yet, alongside the undeniably positive accomplishments across numerous fronts, it has also yielded adverse outcomes. Among these is the misemployment of internet resources by employees, a concern that has garnered the attention of organizational researchers in recent times. The focal point of this study was to pinpoint and prioritize the pivotal catalysts contributing to the emergence of internet procrastination within organizations. This was achieved through the utilization of multi-criteria decision-making techniques among tax employees in Yazd Province. Following an extensive review of research literature, a total of eighteen factors were discerned. Subsequently, to facilitate streamlined managerial strategies aimed at countering this phenomenon, these factors underwent ranking through four techniques: SAW, TOPSIS, ELECTRE, and TOXONOMY. However, due to disparities in the outcomes of these four methodologies, the Copeland method was employed to consolidate the results. The outcomes unveiled that the perception of organizational policies, organizational commitment deficit, excessive leisure time, and role conflict emerged as key influential factors in the manifestation of the internet procrastination phenomenon. Notably, these factors consistently secured prominent positions across all the employed techniques.

Theoretical implications

The perception of organizational policy refers to a situation in which each employee interprets their work environment as a political arena, where individuals endeavor to optimize personal gains and elevate their position and status (Kacmar et al., 1999). The political environment takes shape through the actions of members within the organization and is influenced by policies, operations, and the prevailing organizational culture. Organizations typically do not formally endorse political behavior and often reject this notion as being arbitrary and divisive (Kipnis et al., 1980). Organizational managers and supervisors need to recognize that when employees view their organization as being political in nature, this mindset can lead to adverse outcomes for the organization. Research findings underscore that this factor exerts the most substantial influence on the emergence of the internet procrastination phenomenon among experts within the tax

affairs department. Given the significance of comprehending organizational policies and the far-reaching implications of this perception, it is advisable for managers and supervisors to establish clear organizational regulations and protocols that transparently outline decision-making procedures.

Additionally, policies and procedures pertaining to salary increments, promotions, and career advancements should be clearly delineated for all employees. To mitigate the impact of political connections on promotions and rewards, it is recommended that a well-structured performance evaluation system be employed as the foundation for such matters. This approach ensures that promotions and rewards are based on merit and performance rather than political affiliations.

Within this study, the absence of organizational commitment emerged as the second significant factor. Organizational commitment signifies employees' emotional affinity toward their organization and their alignment, involvement, and active participation within it. This concept encompasses multiple dimensions. Employees exhibiting heightened emotional commitment possess a robust belief in the organization's objectives, values, and mission. On the other hand, individuals displaying elevated levels of normative commitment are motivated to remain within the organization due to their perception of the ethical nature of their (Wong et al., 2023). Organizational commitment holds considerable influence and effectiveness in shaping both individual and collective positive and negative behaviors within the organization (Genevičiūtė-Janonienė & Endriulaitienė, 2014). As individuals' connection to their perceived organization weakens, they tend to engage in alternative activities like internet procrastination. Consequently, organizational managers should endeavor to foster an environment wherein individuals experience commensurate benefits from their exertions and contributions to their role, thereby bolstering their loyalty and commitment to the organization. Alongside this, factors such as ample leisure time and role conflict emerge as noteworthy contributors to the genesis of the internet procrastination phenomenon within organizational settings. Given these dynamics, it becomes imperative for managers to allocate increased attention to human resource management strategies. Implementing approaches like job enrichment, job rotation, and ensuring a harmonious person-job fit can prove pivotal in addressing these challenges. To advance in-depth comprehension, it is recommended that future research delve into qualitative methodologies. These methods would enable the identification of the influential factors underlying the formation of internet procrastination in a more comprehensive manner.

Limitations and Future Directions

This research carries several limitations that could serve as avenues for future investigation. Firstly, the factors recognized by experts might diverge from the actual underlying causes of this phenomenon, given that the experts themselves may not have directly encountered this phenomenon. Secondly, the limited number of participants in the statistical sampling diminishes the scope of generalizability, thereby highlighting the need for a more extensive sample size. Thirdly, the cross-sectional design of the study potentially curtails its applicability to broader contexts. Fourthly, the studied participants primarily consist of individuals with higher incomes. It is worth acknowledging that variables like financial gain from Cyberloafing may exert an influence, warranting further

examination. Lastly, the scope of this study has primarily encompassed minor activities within the realm of Cyberloafing. Future inquiries might be prompted to investigate more serious internet surfing activities, such as online betting, and their potential impact on individual behaviors.

Conclusion

This study embarked on addressing the query regarding the factors that contribute to the emergence of cyberloafing among employees within the Tax Affairs Organization in Yazd province while also identifying their relative importance. Upon analyzing the data, the outcomes unveiled that organizational policy factors, organizational commitment, and an abundance of leisure time exerted the most noteworthy influence on the genesis of the cyberloafing phenomenon, respectively. Conversely, factors such as interpersonal conflict, role overload, and the inclination towards disorder displayed the least impact on the formulation of cyberloafing behavior.

In Iran, a study has been conducted that identified the effective factors and consequences of cyberloafing with the fuzzy Delphi approach. The study's findings delineated the antecedents of cyberloafing across three primary categories: structural, behavioral, and environmental factors. Additionally, the consequences of cyberloafing were categorized into two groups: positive and negative outcomes. (Tehrani et al., 2023).

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